

What are the challenges?

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1. Introduction

Depending on who you talk to, you may hear that big data has failed. Of course there is no correct answer because it also depends on what the question was. Are we asking the right question?

One of the biggest challenges about data is to be able to successfully analyze and understand it in a manner that it is accurate and actionable. In large Organizations, we get carried away with the silos or have lines of business who run their own so called “big data”. However they are dealing with the same customer!

Further what information are we looking for? It makes no sense to go in with a preconceived idea and look for information to justify the decision already made. It is much better to understand your business in its entirety, your objectives for now and the future, but most importantly understand the changing needs of your customer.

The challenge also is to understand the context of that information. Without the context, the information cannot be very useful.

You will hear the approach that can help, the pitfalls that must be avoided as the change in the market place is rapid and one thing is certain that too many Organizations are not keeping pace. This problem gets compounded by the skills gaps and the impact is not just on your customers not being happy, but the bottom-line and cyber security.

You will benefit from this session

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